

IRRI 1995–1996

LISTENING TO THE FARMERS

IRRI

INTERNATIONAL RICE RESEARCH INSTITUTE

Farmers serving farmers in the Mekong Delta

Gene Hettel

TIEN GIANG PROVINCE, VIETNAM

Rice does not give me that much income, but I enjoy doing good things for society by bringing in new technology and spreading it around to my neighbors. In spiritual terms, this is very important to me; profit is secondary,” says Nguyen Van Tai, an irrigated rice farmer in southern Vietnam’s Mekong Delta province of Tien Giang.

Mr. Tai, 50, is an extraordinary person—as one might have already guessed from his philosophy. In the terminology of officials at the University of Can Tho (UC)—Vietnam’s preeminent agricultural school—he is an “advanced farmer,” one of an army of some 4,000 who serve nearly 12 million fellow farmers in the 11-province Mekong Delta region.

Says Dr. Vo-Tong Xuan, UC vice rector and a past member of the IRRI Board of Trustees,

“I first met Mr. Tai in 1976-77 during the biggest outbreak of brown planthopper (BPH) ever to hit the country’s ricefields. He was then a young visionary, armed with a high school agriculture degree, who was among the first few farmers to really understand the value of pest resistance in rice varieties as opposed to pesticide spraying.” (See feature, p 11 and research highlight, p 16.)

“IRRI had already sent some resistant varieties to (the former) South Vietnam in the early 1970s when the first big outbreak hit,” explains Mr. Tai. “So I was well aware of the value of resistance when the second major BPH flare-up struck in 1976. Most farmers in Vietnam will only believe what they see before their eyes. So, when I demonstrated this resistance on my farm, there was no need to use words—I just put out the plots and let the farmers come and see.”

Planting missing hills in the Tai family’s irrigated rice field.

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A. Jovelliana

“I want to thank IRRI for helping Vietnamese farmers to improve their livelihood.”

Nguyen Van Tai and son, Nguyen Bao Thinh, inspect their irrigated rice crop.

Mr. Tai's generosity at that time may have been a major reason disaster was avoided. "It was right after the war and we had no money at the University," says Dr. Xuan. "He used his own funds to set up the demonstration plots. It was from his fields—and later from those of his neighbors—that we were able to prove to the farmers deeper in the Delta that the answer is not chemicals, but varietal resistance."

Twenty years later, Mr. Tai still allocates 0.15 of a hectare of his small 0.8-hectare farm to field experiments and observation plots for his neighbors to evaluate. He devotes the rest of his holdings to multiplying seed of newly selected lines, which he sells or trades to some 300 farmers in his district. "Over the years," says Mr. Tai, "I have tested nearly 500 lines and improved varieties (mostly IRRI

materials obtained from UC and the Cuu Long Delta Rice Research Institute) of which I have selected about 40 varieties of various durations and then have multiplied for distribution.” IR53915 and IR55606 are two varieties that he has recently selected; both are currently being multiplied. “These varieties have the short duration that Delta farmers are looking for,” he says.

Although in most years the family has been lucky to break

even on the farm, Mr. Tai and his wife have raised and supported five daughters and four sons. Most of the children are grown now—several girls married, one son a tailor, and another a tax collector. He has hopes that his youngest boy, Nguyen Bao Thinh, 11, will take over from him someday and continue the family’s tradition of service to the farmers of the district.

Mr. Tai, who is not yet quite ready to retire, has a message for IRRI scientists. He says, “I want

to thank IRRI for helping Vietnamese farmers to improve their livelihood over the past 20 years—but your work and our work is not finished. New varieties should have built-in BPH and blast resistance, combined with a short duration (around 90 days), like IR53915, so that we can grow three crops per year. And of course, we need higher grain quality so that our harvest will get a better price on the export market.” ■

Rice and fish: a perfect pair

The advanced farmer couple of Mr. Duong Trung Buu and Ms. Nguyen Thi Hong take an early afternoon break to discuss their remaining work for the day.

Their 0.35-hectare farm in Thanh Binh District of Dong Thap Province on the fringe of the Plain of Reeds features a rice - fish operation. After transplanting the first rice crop, they stock the field/pond with four silver carp and six tilapia per square meter of surface area, around 400 fish in all.

“We feed the fish rice bran and broken rice mixed with thinly shredded floating weeds,” says Ms. Hong. “They can also feed on the algae that cling to the floating weeds. It takes them 10 months to reach harvest size.” After harvesting the current rice crop, they will plant a second early rainy season crop and then harvest it with the fish when the fish price is higher.

“We use a stiff-strawed rice variety in the fish pond so that the crop will not lodge,” says Ms. Hong. “That’s one thing we don’t want to feed to the fish.”

Mr. Buu, 47, a collaborator with UC since 1978, has tested some 300 lines and selected around 20 for multiplying and distributing to the 100 farmers he serves in the district. “Currently, I’m selecting for resistance to blast, sheath blight, and the new BPH biotype,” he says. “Of course, I’m also looking for high yield and better quality for export.”

G. Hirtzel

Farmers test delayed, reduced spraying in Vietnam

Gene Hettel

MEKONG DELTA, VIETNAM

The recovery of the plants has been amazing," Mr. Vo Van Ba tells Mr. Phan Van Mot, a neighboring farmer, and Mr. Pham Van Thai, an IPM official at the nearby Cai Lay District Plant Protection Station in Tien Giang Province, Vietnam. They are standing in a rice plot where Mr. Ba has delayed insecticide application for 40 days and now there is little if any evidence of earlier leaffolder damage to the foliage. (See highlight, p 16.)

Although quite skeptical at first, Mr. Ba and his wife Ha had agreed to devote about one-third of their 0.3-hectare rice farm to an insecticide experiment promoted by the Station. First, Mr. Ba and about 30 other farmers took a short training course offered by Mr. Thai to learn the pesticide delay technique and understand why it works. Then he and his wife were invited to participate in the research and demonstration phase.

"In the early going, leaf damage by feeding leaffolders made our IR64 crop look very miserable," says Mr. Ba. "Other farmers asked why we did not spray. At the time, I was ashamed to tell them that we were participating in the experiment."

"They were almost on the verge of spraying—as some participating farmers did when they feared the worst upon

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seeing the initial damage," says Mr. Thai, who has instructed around 150 farmers in five separate training courses in Cai Lay District. "But I encouraged them not to and, bravely, they did not. Now as you can see, the rice has fully recovered and I doubt if Mr. and Mrs. Ba will find any yield difference between the experimental plot and the rest of their farm, which received the normal pesticide application."

Says Mr. Ba: "Mr. Thai assured us that everything would be all right, so we did not spray even when our neighbors pressured us to do so. Now, I will tell anyone who will listen that the idea is sound."

Meanwhile, one pesticide company has stepped up a campaign in the area that advises

Phan Van Mot, Vo Van Ba (center), and Pham Van Thai inspect a field where pesticide application was delayed for 40 days.

using insecticide and emphasizes a critical spraying period during the first 40 days. Says Mr. Pham Van Khai, chief of the Party Committee of Cai Lay District, "This is confusing some farmers listening to the radio when, for instance, a farm program discusses the new technologies and then immediately following is a chemical advertisement that advises an opposing strategy. I may complain to the radio station management about this," he says, "but I know it is very difficult for station management to turn down advertising income." ■

Stabilizing upland rice production in Lao PDR

Gene Hettel

XIENGNUEN DISTRICT, LAO PDR

Ou-Phuang Duangprajit, a long-time upland rice farmer in Luang Prabang Province, Lao PDR, had passed by the Houay Khot Agricultural Research Station numerous times. Recently, he got a first-hand look at what actually happens on this 19-hectare experimental farm used as a base for the upland component of the National Rice Research Program and the Lao-IRRI Research and Training Project, supported by the Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation.

Mr. Boonmali, the district agricultural officer, had identified Mr. Ou-Phuang and his wife, Sao

Hen, and 24 other families in the region as progressive upland farmers who might be interested in providing their expertise and some of their land for on-farm research. He invited the farmers to see technologies that were being tried out on the experimental farm as alternatives to slashing and burning the countryside to make way for rice and other crops.

Says Mr. Ou-Phuang, "My wife and I are very interested in cooperating with the researchers because we want to adopt management practices that will enable our family to grow rice on the same land year after year and provide our lives with some stability."

R. Calderon

R. Calderon

As much as Ou-Phuang Duangprajit would like to stay and assist with the farm work, he must go off and try to earn additional money for his family.

D. Rifaat / A. Riccauto

Agricultural production in Lao PDR is dominated by rice, a staple food in the Lao diet. Nowhere in Asia is upland rice more important than in this heavily forested, landlocked country where this ecosystem makes up about 31 percent of the total rice area, accounting for between 20 and 22 percent of production. The prevailing mode of cultivation is slash-and-burn, which is practiced by some 300,000 ethnic minority farmers, such as the Ou-Phuang family.

In mid- to late May, the Lao hills present an energetic scene as farmers and their families rush to plant their rice crop.

It is a way of life based on tree felling and bush burning to clear land for cultivation. After 1 or 2 years, families move their cultivation to another area and start the process again. It takes years for the vegetation to return. Airline passengers flying the 400-kilometer route north from Vientiane to Luang Prabang can

The effects of slash-and-burn agriculture are readily evident to air travelers between Vientiane and Luang Prabang.

joined the Project as upland agronomist in February 1996, and his agronomist counterparts at Houay Khot Station, Mr. Boonthanh Keoboulapha and Mr. Soulasith Maniphone, were delighted that 17 of the 24 farm families volunteered to get involved in the on-farm research for the coming season.

Only the farmland of Mr. Ou-Phuang and Ms. Sao Hen met the experimental requirements of being first- or second-year ricefields (following fallow) that are not extremely steep, about 1 hectare in area, and a short distance from the road for others to see. However, rejection of the other farmers' fields for the experiments did not douse their enthusiasm—they helped locate suitable fields belonging to others who were also interested in on-farm research.

In 1962, when he was five years old, Mr. Ou-Phuang came to Xiengnguen District with his mother and father. They are Khamu ethnic people of the Lao Theung (farmers of the midland mountain slopes) who were refugees from the Indochina War—against the French—in the eastern part of the country. The thickly forested area was a popular haven for war refugees of various ethnic groups throughout the 1960s and early 1970s—and is a major reason why the land is being stretched to the limit today.

Mr. Ou-Phuang and Ms. Sao Hen currently have three 1-hectare upland fields on which they grow food for their family

immediately see the consequences of the destructive practice (see photo).

According to Mr. Bouathong Phounsalit, head of the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry's Rural Development Committee, some 250,000-300,000 hectares of land—of which 100,000 are rain forest—are cleared by slash-and-burn every year. In an attempt to drastically reduce this onslaught on the country's invaluable forest resources, the government has begun a land reallocation program in which upland families are provided with up to four pieces of land, from 1 to 1.5 hectares each (contingent on family size).

Mr. Viengsavanh Manivong, national program coordinator of the Lao-IRRI Project, says, "Families should stay on this land and no longer slash-and-burn into new areas. We also urge farmers to grow rice on only one parcel of land at any one time and to rotate nonrice crops such as maize and mungbean on the others or leave them fallow altogether," he says.

For this scheme to work, management practices unfamiliar to the farmers will have to be adopted. And that's where one component of the Lao-IRRI Project will be playing a major role. Dr. Keith Fahrney, who

of four children, ranging in age from 1 to 16, and both sets of grandparents.

In addition to growing just one traditional variety of non-glutinous rice (called *mu*), the family is also growing some bananas, vegetables, and maize to supplement their diet. “Last year we planted some teak,” says Ms. Sao Hen proudly. Like many farmers, the couple sees the valuable forest tree as an insurance policy, which will be cashed in for their children some 20 years in the future.

The family was very anxious to get the on-farm research started this year so that they could begin improving the soil of their worn-out land. In the experiment, the Lao-IRRI agronomists are trying to make the fallow more efficient by using a legume in the dry season

so that the land is not taken out of production.

They planted their traditional variety using the normal practice of dropping seed into holes made by dibble sticks. After the last of at least four weedings, Ms. Sao Hen will sow seed of a legume known as stylo (*Stylosanthes guianensis*) under the standing rice crop on half of the 32 plots, each measuring 8 × 10 meters. Prior to planting the 1997 crop, the agronomists will test four residue management treatments on both the farmer-practice and legume-improved fallow plots: burning, mulching, removing, and grazing.

“As much I would like to stay and assist with the work, I must go off and try to earn additional money for my family,” Mr. Ou-Phuang says. He is home now only to help with the rice plant-

ing and to confer with his wife and Lao-IRRI agronomists about implementing the experiments. “Tomorrow, I must leave to find dried fish, cloth, monosodium glutamate—anything I can purchase cheaply—for resale in distant villages,” he says. Such is the circumstance of many farmers in the Lao uplands.

Dr. Fahrney concludes: “Farmers are willing to shift to a more sedentary agricultural system—they just don’t know how. Farmers and researchers working together for a common solution seems to be the best way to go about finding sustainable methods for upland rice production.” ■

Planting, hand weeding, and building and maintaining bamboo fences keep Sao Hen and her family busy throughout the year.

Farmers and researchers work together in the Malagasy highlands

Carolyn Dedolph

AMBODIAVIAY, MID WEST REGION, MADAGASCAR

Like many of their neighbors, Razafiman-dimby, 52, and Blandine Razafimanantsoa, 46, immigrated years ago to this highland region, where the sky seems to be higher and bluer than anywhere else on earth.

The couple have nine children, ranging in age from 10 to 26; four are already married; another four are still in school. All help out on the farm.

The family grows rice, cassava, maize, groundnut, and peanut on 4.5 hectares of uplands, and rainfed rice on 2 hectares of lowlands. They also raise cattle, swine, and chickens. Says Mr. Razafiman-dimby: "When we first arrived here in 1962, we grew rice on 1 hectare of lowland—all the land we had at the time. We've been growing upland rice since 1976."

Success—in Malagasy terms—has come, but not without much backache and determination. A quick look around the farm is proof. In front of their large two-story clay house, groundnuts, peanuts, and rice are spread on the ground in geometric patterns, drying in the intense sunlight. A crude verandah juts out from the second level. The first level serves as a granary to store dried

rice and maize for eating. It doubles as a place for the free-ranging hens to lay their eggs.

"We keep the seeds for planting upstairs near the ceiling—to keep them dry," explains Ms. Razafimanantsoa. The upstairs area is divided into two sparsely furnished rooms, both with dried mud and straw floors covered with mats in some places. Bible-story comic sheets adorn the walls. Five children and the parents sleep here; the others sleep in a nearby second, but smaller, structure built to accommodate the overflow of children.

Since 1986, researchers from the National Center for Research Applied to Rural Development (FOFIFA) have been working with the family on new varieties and techniques for use on the farm.

FOFIFA has been doing on-farm trials in maize, upland rice, lowland rice, and in controlling weeds in upland rice.

Hand weeding is a back-breaking job that men, women, and even children must do—at least twice each season in every upland field. In an effort to control weeds, the farmers have experimented with using a cono weeder in comparison with a traditional rotary weeder, says Ms. Razafimanantsoa. The testing

Groundnuts, peanuts, and rice are sun dried around the family's house.

was done in conjunction with the Madagascar-IRRI Project.

The couple also tried trap and catch crop methods of controlling the parasitic weed called *Striga*. Peanuts, sunflower, and soybeans were tested on the farm. Other control measures were plowing under maize when the *Striga* appeared, and planting pigeon pea, which stayed on the field for two seasons. When the pigeon pea was harvested, it had the added effect of green

manure, which increased the yield of the rice crop planted afterward.

The family helped IRRI and FOFIFA scientists design an experiment that compared the yields of various varieties and transplanting dates using different weed control treatments. They have also done on-farm research with FOFIFA and IRRI to test several traditional and modern varieties: 2366 (IAC25), and Brazilian

“We do on-farm research to get some knowledge. We learn how to use new techniques in managing crops, like transplanting in a line, instead of at random.”

R. Cabrera

R. Cabrera

The future weighs heavily on the shoulders of Razafimandimby (top) and Blandine (bottom) and their nine children.

varieties 3737 (CNA4196, locally known as Telorirana), 3730 (CNA4137, called Mavolamba), and 3759 (Murium Liguie, known as Maintiloha). While these were introduced to Madagascar by French researchers, the on-farm testing was funded by the Madagascar-IRRI Project.

The family keeps seeds for planting from the trials, which

they continue to do with FOFIFA and IRRI.

As collaborators, they told the FOFIFA and IRRI scientists which varieties and techniques they didn't like—and why. For example, one variety was difficult to sell because of its unacceptable taste.

“We do on-farm research to get some knowledge,” the farmer

explains. “We learn how to use new techniques in managing crops, like transplanting in a line, instead of at random. We now know about seedbed management and about not planting too many seeds.

“We get to try the new varieties, and the cono and rotary weeders. The weeders are very good, but they are difficult to make locally and must be ordered from Tana (the capital city),” he continues. A simple rotary weeder is on Mr. Razafimandimby's wish list.

Despite advances, farmers in Madagascar still face some very basic production problems. As soil fertility continues to decrease, one of the major concerns is fertilizer, which is very expensive. Farmers apply farmyard manure but it is of poor quality. Mr. Razafimandimby says that they need techniques on how to obtain manure that will give more reliable results.

The future weighs heavily on the couple's shoulders. “When we came here, we were only two. Now there are 11 of us. We don't know what to do,” Mr. Razafimandimby confides. “We would like the children to stay in farming but, because of our limited area, it will not be possible. Maybe there will be 20 or 30 of us in the future. We know that there is still free land available elsewhere, but it is not necessarily safe and security is not guaranteed.”

As the couple reflects, they try to laugh at their situation.

“Despite our problems, life is improving. At least my family has enough rice to eat,” Mr. Razafimandimby concludes. ■

IPM—Malagasy style: maize tempts crickets away from rice

Maize keeps crickets away from upland rice.

MAHASOLO, MID WEST, MADAGASCAR

Joseph Rakotoarisoa and wife Julienne Raharisoa grow their upland rice using the simple principle that “crickets may like rice, but they like maize even better.” An excellent example of indigenous integrated pest management (IPM), the couple has intercropped maize with rice in their upland fields for the past 15 years.

The success of this strategy is evident in their bountiful rice harvest. Of course, they still usually have some maize to harvest as well if the crickets aren't too hungry.

The family plants 3 hectares of upland rice, a little less than 1 hectare of cassava, and 1.3 hectares of lowland rice. They use two FOFIFA-released varieties: 2366 on the uplands and 2787 on the lowlands. In earlier times, they used traditional varieties.

“We sell most of our upland rice and only keep some back for seed,” says Mr. Rakotoarisoa.

Hand threshing rice.

The family uses a marketing strategy that is difficult to beat: they raise mostly upland rice, which sells at a price premium over regular rice. They also market their rice when the price is highest. Rather than selling it immediately after harvest (May-July) when prices are lowest, they store it and sell from November to March—when prices peak.

Scientists seek weed-killing rice plants

Weeds are the most serious biological constraint in upland rice production. IRRI scientists are now pursuing projects to learn how to manage weeds with less labor. One approach is to search for rice cultivars that exhibit a characteristic called allelopathy.

According to Dr. Maria Olofsdotter, IRRI affiliate scientist, allelopathic plants can prevent the growth of nearby plants through the production of biological compounds they release into the environment. “We are currently looking for allelopathic rices that inhibit the growth of weeds detrimental to rice production,” she says. “If we are successful, we might be able—through breeding—to develop rice cultivars that control weeds themselves and thus help reduce one of the rice farmer’s most time-consuming chores.”

In field experiments during the 1995 wet and dry seasons, Dr. Olofsdotter has found several rice cultivars—including AC1423, Kouketsumuchi, Musashikogane, Taichung Native 1, Woo Co Chin Yu, Tangan, YH1, and Takanenishiki—that can reduce the dry weight of the annual weedy grass, *Echinochloa crus-galli*, by more than 50 percent. “These cultivars also reduced root length of germinating weed seedlings by 50 percent in laboratory tests aimed at studying allelopathic effects,” she says.

These preliminary studies indicate that rice allelopathy can be used for weed suppression under

Weed suppression through allelopathy is aimed at reducing the drudgery of hand weeding upland rice, a backbreaking chore done primarily by women.

field conditions. Experiments are continuing in this very intriguing approach to controlling weeds.

Upland breeders face special challenges

Rice breeders are challenged by the extremely varied agroecology and socioeconomic aspects of the upland environment. “The uplands worldwide are much too diverse for one or two varieties to be grown on millions of hectares as can be done in the irrigated ecosystem,” says Dr. Brigitte Courtois, a breeder seconded from the French Center for International Cooperation in Development-oriented Agricultural Research (CIRAD-CA).

The criteria that make a “good” upland variety for a Filipino, a Thai, or an Indian farmer are often contradictory. “Even different ethnic groups in the same country, such as in the hills of northern Lao PDR, have irreconcilable views on what constitutes ideal grain for their upland varieties,” says Dr. Lisa Price, IRRI anthropologist.

To work with this diversity, upland rice breeders have created homogeneous subecosystems in which to target germplasm development. But even within each subecosystem,

varietal performance changes substantially from site to site. According to Dr. Courtois, more than 50 percent of the yield variation of a variety across sites can be attributed to these genotype by environment (GxE) interactions.

“We are solving this problem by breeding fewer upland varieties at IRRI and more at national research system stations,” says Dr. Courtois. “This decentralization reaches all levels and involves ever-increasing farmer participation.”

The end result will be a “basket of germplasm” containing individual varieties with good specific adaptability for all possible niches instead of one favored, unique variety which has that, up-to-now, elusive broad adaptability.

Better understanding of G×E interactions in upland rice

To obtain a better understanding of the nature of the GxE interactions that make upland rice breeding so complex (see above), a common trial was established that evaluated a set of 12 core varieties over 3 consecutive years at 11 representative sites in six countries.

The GxE interactions were analyzed using additive main effects and multiplicative interaction (AMMI) biometrical models, which allow for the detection and quantification of more general forms of GxE interaction than do the classical models.

Such analysis can quantify the respective importance of the genotype (G), the environment (E), and the GxE interactions and help match specifically adapted varieties with appropriate sites.

According to Dr. Graham McLaren, head of the IRRI Biometrics Unit, major factors influencing GxE interactions can be identified by looking for relationships between interaction scores estimated for each environment from the AMMI model and environmental characterization data including soil properties, climatic conditions, and cropping system information. "Using this technique, we established the importance of soil chemistry and rainfall patterns at sowing and at flowering with the first year's data," he says.

Pattern analysis, which extends AMMI models by incorporating a clustering component and allowing more general data scaling, was used to identify groups of sites with common GxE patterns. This should make the exchange of breeding material more successful. Says CIRAD-CA breeder Dr. Brigitte Courtois: "We will be able to choose better testing sites that represent the widest possible diversity and eliminate redundancies at the same time."

The trial, which initially involved only the main upland rice-breeding sites worldwide, will be extended to all upland rice-testing sites through collaboration with the International Network for Genetic Evaluation of Rice. This effort should ultimately contribute to increased efficiency and decreased cost of upland rice breeding programs.

Photo: C. Chantrea

Fighting nematodes with crop rotation

Root-parasitic nematodes are omnipresent in upland rice production systems. "Root lesion nematodes (*Pratylenchus* species) and root knot nematodes (*Meloidogyne* species), which are widespread in these agricultural systems, have the highest potential to cause economic damage," says Dr. Jean-Claude Prot, a visiting nematologist.

Because the nematodes themselves are so small, most infestations remain unnoticed by upland farmers—even if the pests are constraining yields. "However, if they are identified to be a problem, they can be controlled by using resistant varieties and crop rotation systems with nonhost crops," says Dr. Prot.

Recently, the scientist identified the weed *Ageratum conyzoides* as a harbinger of a root knot nematode (*M. graminicola*) in Indonesia, Thailand, and Lao PDR—which may be the reason Lao upland farmer Sahai Boua has been noticing yellowing in his rice. His family's 1.5 hectares have an overabundance of *A. conyzoides*. "This is the main reason we want to do a rotation

Surrounded by the weed *Ageratum conyzoides*, Keith Fahrney and Sahai Boua discuss the rotation experiment that will suppress both the weed and the nematodes harbored by it.

experiment on that farm," says Dr. Keith Fahrney, upland agronomist with the Lao-IRRI project. (See feature, p 20.)

Evidence exists that rotations of different plants, such as maize and peanut, can help cut down the nematode populations. Because of the rotation experiment designed for his farm, Mr. Boua will, for the first time in 1996, be planting nonrice crops on portions of his land. Previously these areas were destined for fallow, where *A. conyzoides* provided a home for the nematodes until rice was planted again.

Mr. Boua has decided to plant an improved variety of maize (Hat Dok Keo 4) as his cash crop and peanut as his soil improvement crop. "Perhaps my rice yields will increase as a result," says Mr. Boua hopefully. "At the same time, peanuts will help make my soil more fertile, which will enable my family to stay on this land for years to come." ■

A hectic harvest/planting time for Central Javan farmers

Gene Hettel

JAKENAN, INDONESIA

The late February sun has just come out from behind the dark rain clouds that had deposited a brief mid-afternoon shower over the rainfed lowland ricefields of Central Java. Now, thousands of farmers, their families, and contract laborers resume the rice harvest of what the locals call the *gogorancab* (the direct-seeded, first crop of the October-February wet season).

Some busily respread the just-harvested grains on plastic tarpaulins stretched on the ground to use the sun's drying rays. Others, who have already completed their harvest, are preparing the land for receiving the *walik jerami* (transplanted, second crop) or are already placing the seedlings in the ground. This scene stretches to the horizon on some 25,000 hectares in and around Pati District. The average field size (either owned or rented) of a farm family in this region is around 0.5 hectare.

Laborers are expensive.

Near the town of Jakenan, Mr. Seman and one of his young sons, Sutarso, supervise seven laborers as the harvest progresses on their 0.1-hectare rented field. Several women cut bundles of rice panicles and bring them to a small foot-pedal thresher. Mr. Seman and his son count the sacks as they are filled. "We'll get about 25 sacks from this crop," Mr. Seman predicts. This will

Central Javan farmers quickly transplant the *walik jerami* rice crop to use as much available moisture as possible.

Mr. Seman (left) worries about the cost of his contract laborers (below).

A. Javellana

later shrink to about 22 sacks, weighing around 40 kilograms each, after the grain is sun-dried to a storable moisture content.

Although it appears that a bumper crop is at hand, Mr. Seman has numerous expenses. Since his family is small, he must hire contract laborers. “These

seven will cost me 28,000 rupiahs (about US\$12.75) today plus their three meals,” he laments. Weed control is another major cost for the gogoranch crop. “Hiring about 10 women to hand weed my field, usually three times between October and January, has already cost me

“I hope I will be able to keep enough of this harvest to feed my family.”

3 tons on his 0.4-hectare field. He is hurriedly preparing his land for transplanting the walik jerami. "I want to take advantage of late rains that sometimes continue into June," he says. Rainfall during the wet season in Pati District can be very unpredictable and can have drastic effects on crop performance, particularly the walik jerami.

His variety of choice, IR64, often approaches or exceeds 8 tons per hectare for the gogoranchah. "My walik jerami crop of

Mr. Sumijan (above) and Mr. Sucipto (below) contemplate the rice harvesting and planting activities that must be compressed over a period of just a few days.

Rp 20,000 (US\$9.10)," Mr. Seman calculates. Add to this the Rp 200,000 (US\$90) for annual rental of the field and the 52-year-old farmer will be forced to sell a substantial part of his crop just to pay his bills. "I hope I will be able to keep enough of this harvest to feed my family," he says.

Because he has had to wait his turn for the laborers to arrive at his field, he is somewhat behind some of his neighbors, who are already busily establishing the walik jerami crop. Nearby, a bed of IR64 seedlings awaits transplanting, which will take place as soon as the land can be prepared, because every day's delay means valuable moisture lost and a reduced yield for the year's second crop that will grow during the Central Javan dry season.

Taking advantage of the rain. In another part of Pati District, Mr. Sumijan, 60, a life-long farmer, has already harvested his gogoranchah—

IR64 rarely exceeds 1.5 tons of grain per hectare,” he says, “however, the truly important product of the second crop is the rice straw, which will get my cattle through the dry season when no grass is available.”

Mr. Sumijan, whose four children are now grown and on their own, does not need as much rice as he used to for home consumption. “I will not sell my gogorancha harvest right away, but will hold most of it—maybe into December—when I will get a better market price.” Weeds are his most costly problem during the gogorancha season. “I must pay contract laborers as much as Rp 80,000 (US\$36) to hand weed my field at least twice,” he says regretfully.

Family teamwork. Farther down the road, the family and neighbors of Mr. Supar Hadi Sucipto have a set routine in which all participants have vital roles in getting the walik jerami crop established as soon as possible on his 0.2 hectare. Mr. Sucipto, his wife, and father use large *paculs* (hoes) to turn over the stubble left from the gogorancha harvested just a few days before. Neighbor children bundle seedlings and deliver them to his teenage daughters, who do the laborious transplanting. Due to the efficient teamwork, an amazing area is tilled and transplanted in a very brief period of time (see photo, p 30-31).

Mr. Sucipto hopes the rains will continue to be plentiful this season so his walik jerami will produce a good crop of both grain and straw. “I had a reasonably good grain yield of 6.6 tons per hectare for my gogorancha this season, but I

have a lot of mouths to feed and a superior walik jerami might allow me to sell some rice later in the year,” he says. Mole crickets and weeds are the biggest headaches for the Suciptos. The family will repay their neighbors’ help tomorrow by working in their fields.

Collaborating with IRRI.

Around the bend, Mr. Juwandi stands in one of his freshly transplanted walik jerami fields with Dr. Maddala Murty, project scientist in IRRI’s Soil and Water Sciences Division. They are discussing what will need to be

replicate the experiment here in Mr. Juwandi’s field,” explains Dr. Murty. This involves checking the lateral water flow with vertical plastic barriers that are placed at strategic points across the bunds.

At first, Dr. Murty had difficulty finding the right field for his experiment. “I spent several days surveying the Jakenan region looking for the long, narrow piece of ground I would need to properly conduct the experiment. I was almost ready to give up when my driver, who turned out to be

done in an on-farm experiment Mr. Juwandi has agreed to participate in.

In 1995, Dr. Murty conducted experiments at the nearby Jakenan Experiment Station that show lateral flow in the soil is possibly a more important factor in water loss than percolation in the rainfed lowlands of the Jakenan region. “To confirm this hypothesis, I am about to

Dr. Maddala Murty (right) reviews an on-farm experiment with collaborating farmer Mr. Juwandi.

Mr. Juwandi, said, ‘Why don’t you use one of my fields?’ Mr. Juwandi is happy to collaborate with IRRI. “I feel my contribution to agricultural research is now much more substantial than just being a driver for the experiment station,” he says proudly. ■

Farmers learn from on-farm research

Carolyn Dedolph

RAJSHAHI, BANGLADESH

Outside of the city, one side of the road is lush and green with irrigated dry season rice. The other side is fallow, dusty, and brown—there's not even enough water for the weeds. The farmers who work this land, who follow the traditional cropping pattern of growing only one crop of wet season rice a year, must wait for the rain to come in July before planting.

Now, thanks to deep tube wells, the cropping pattern has been shifting around Rajshahi to irrigated dry season rice followed by a rainfed wet season crop—and dramatically increasing output.

Mr. Mohamed Majid Uddin and his family are collaborators with the Rainfed Lowland Rice Research Consortium. Rajshahi, which means “king’s place”, is one of the Consortium’s five key sites.

The head of family, who was away when we visited, has been farming for nearly 25 years with his wife. His sons, Salah Uddin, 28, and Omar Faruk, 25, are actively involved in the farm. There are 11 children in the family, although two of the young men are no longer at home. All of the children have studied through secondary school.

“We are getting educated to help our father in agriculture,” says Salah, who has a master’s degree. But he really hopes to get a job in industry some day. Meanwhile, he and Omar supervise the laborers working in the fields.

The family has been collaborating with Consortium researchers on direct dry seeding of rice. They became involved in on-farm research because their father is interested in rice research and motivated to participate, says Salah.

R. Cabrera

And yes, the sons know about IRRI. Recites Salah: “IRRI is an international institute that does research on rice.” The goal of the family’s current collaborative work is to spread the potential risk of drought damage by carrying out four seedings over 2 months.

“Seeding is done every 15 days,” explains Salah. “The first one is done around the first of June, then a second in a different plot around June 15.” Two more seedings follow.

Salah Uddin helps his father on the farm, but his real dream is to work in industry.

R. Cabrera

“We are interested in doing on-farm research in the years to come. If the trials are successful, we’ll continue to collaborate. We are learning many things from the work.”

D. Rilligesi & J. Reulenco

The first seeding was done in a dry field and didn’t germinate well. When the first rains finally came, however, the fields turned green. The fourth seeding was a little late, and a drought came during flowering.

The first, second, and third seedings produced a good yield: 3.5-4 tons per hectare. “This technique helps to eliminate the risk of drought because there’s no need to determine the best time to seed,” Salah says.

Excessive weeds, however, are a limitation with direct seeding during the wet season, he points out. Normally, the soil is puddled and seedlings

Thanks to deep tube wells, farmers in Rajshahi can now grow an irrigated dry season rice crop followed by a rainfed wet season crop, dramatically increasing output.

that are about one month old are transplanted.

“We’ll experiment again in the next wet season, which starts in July. This time we’ll do two or three seedings on 2 *bighas* (0.26 hectare),” Salah says. Three or four days after harvesting the crop in November, the family will plant chickpea to take advantage of residual moisture.

The family’s biggest constraint is water. “If there’s no water, we cannot plant,” explains Salah. He also mentions that fertilizer is often not available and insects and diseases sometimes cause losses. They use a granular insecticide to combat stem borer.

“We are interested in doing on-farm research in the years to come. If the trials are successful, we’ll continue to collaborate,” says Salah. “We are learning many things from the work.” ■

Shaking up theories about blast pathogen diversity

In three valleys of western Bhutan, an unprecedented outbreak of rice blast disease occurred in 1995. Farmers lost their entire crops to the disease in the most severely affected areas.

Although commonly observed in fields in Bhutan, blast had apparently never before caused serious losses. So why then?

“DNA fingerprinting of the blast pathogen (*Magnaporthe grisea*) revealed an extremely diverse population in the affected areas. So a novel introduction wasn't the reason for the epidemic,” says Dr. Robert Zeigler, IRRI plant pathologist.

After talking with farmers and examining weather records, scientists concluded that unusual weather at critical crop stages probably triggered the indigenous pathogen population to explode into an epidemic.

But there may be more to it than that. Earlier work by Dr. Zeigler and his colleagues to characterize the blast pathogen population in the Himalayas of India revealed genetic diversity far greater than that of populations previously studied.

“There's strong evidence that sexual recombination may be occurring in the field,” Dr. Zeigler says. “This finding challenges assumptions that *M. grisea* reproduces strictly by cloning itself and that different lineages are genetically isolated.”

The implication: even apparently simple blast pathogen populations in the Himalayas may be the source of new types of pathogen that could potentially threaten millions of hectares of rice growing in the Gangetic plains.

When an unprecedented outbreak of rice blast disease occurred in Bhutan, Robert Zeigler (left) went to investigate the reasons.

C. Zeigler

Characterizing rainfed lowlands accurately

For years, scientists who have tried to characterize the rainfed lowland rice areas of the world have ended up frustrated.

The sheer diversity and unpredictability of the climate make it extremely difficult to reliably classify the rainfed lowland areas into a particular subecosystem category of favorable, submergence-prone, drought-prone, or drought- and submergence-prone.

“A given area could be classified as being in one subecosystem this year but in a different subecosystem the next year,” explains Dr. Virendra P. Singh, IRRI agronomist. “Consequently, scientists could not develop a technology and recommend it with confidence to farmers.”

But things have changed for the better. Using remote sensing and geographic information systems, Dr. Singh and his collaborators developed a new methodology to reliably characterize and delineate an area into a subecosystem category.

Twenty-four districts covering about 3 million hectares in eastern Uttar Pradesh, and some districts in Bihar, Madhya Pradesh, and Assam, India, were used to test the methodology in a massive collaborative effort involving researchers from the Indian Council of Agricultural Research, agricultural universities in India, and IRRI; workers from state remote-sensing application centers and nongovernment organizations; and farmers.

“We found that in 9 out of 10 cases, the classification derived using this system is correct,” Dr. Singh says.

Scientists can now pinpoint where specific technologies will be useful for farmers—and just as importantly, where they will not. “For example, varieties with tolerance for drought can be recommended—with confidence—as appropriate for an area. This couldn't be previously done,” Dr. Singh says.

Rainfed lowland rice varieties and associated crop management techniques are now being tested in farmers' fields in eastern India based on these new classifications.

Expanding the research base

After only 5 years' of existence, the Rainfed Lowland Rice Research Consortium (RLRRC) is having a major impact on its targeted ecosystem.

The challenges facing the Consortium are huge, including increasing productivity, sustaining these increases, and doing so with technologies that could be adopted by resource-poor farmers.

"Consortium scientists are working to expand and strengthen the research base for the rainfed lowland rice ecosystem to generate new technologies that have local, regional, and international applications," says Dr. Robert Zeigler, leader of IRRI's Rainfed Lowland Rice Ecosystem Program. IRRI joined forces with relatively strong national agricultural research systems (NARSs) from Bangladesh, India, Indonesia, the Philippines, and Thailand to form the Consortium. Initially funded only by the Asian Development Bank (ADB), the consortium now also enjoys the support of the Dutch Government.

Participating institutions have embraced the multidisciplinary research model embodied in the consortium approach and have restructured their relevant programs accordingly. As a result, there are now fully decentralized rainfed lowland rice breeding programs in northeast Thailand, Indochina, and eastern India.

"These programs built upon local farmers' knowledge and germplasm, and now have highly productive, adapted, advanced lines under evaluation in farmers' fields," Dr. Zeigler says.

"The Consortium is really a major step in the evolution of CGIAR and NARS partnerships in research,"

says Dr. Zeigler. "It has now reached the stage where complex and potentially high-payoff strategic research is being conducted in a truly collaborative mode."

Farmer-participatory breeding

Why aren't more farmers using modern rainfed rice varieties? The question is a serious one for breeders. They realize that the rainfed rice environments are complex and that their breeding strategies must take this complexity into account.

"Farmer input to the breeding process can be most useful in the beginning, at the problem identification stage, and in the later phases of selection," says Dr. Ken Fischer, IRRI deputy director general for research. "This will help to ensure that rice varieties developed are selected and evaluated for specific adaptation to farm microenvironments."

During a "think-tank" meeting on farmer-participatory breeding at IRRI in March 1996, participants from around the world shared experiences and discussed expectations of farmer participatory breeding projects. Scientists, research managers, farmers, and government and nongovernment representatives attended.

IRRI scientists have been making use of the farmer-participatory breeding concept for some time now. Advanced breeding lines originating from the Thai-IRRI Shuttle Program are being tested in farmers' fields in northeastern Thailand and in eastern India. Lines from populations developed using modern and traditional varieties are under evaluation and selection in farmers' field in Bangladesh.

Perfecting direct dry seeding of rice

Scientists and farmers are working together to perfect the practice of dry seeding rice. The ultimate goal is to get more farmers—where appropriate—to adopt this economical, time-saving establishment technique in which rice seeds are broadcast directly in dry plowed or moist unpuddled fields.

In four villages in Pangasinan Province, Philippines, dry seeded rice systems were found to outperform transplanted systems. Although rice yields were similar in the two systems, dry seeded rice farms produced higher total annual income because enough residual soil moisture remains to grow mungbean after rice. "Dry seeded rice uses rainfall more efficiently than transplanted rice," says Dr. Sadiq Bhuiyan, IRRI water resource specialist.

After sowing, dry seeds can remain viable in dry soil for 15-20 days. They germinate with the first significant rains. "In the transplanted rice culture, rice cannot be established until enough rain has accumulated for plowing and puddling" says Dr. To Phuc Tuong, IRRI water management engineer. So by dry seeding, farmers could gain a month or two that otherwise would be spent preparing land, allowing them to potentially grow a second crop.

Farmers can also benefit from another simple practice. In a different study, research on 50 farms showed that, through better land leveling and bund management, yields of dry seeded rice would be increased by about 1 ton per hectare. "Rainwater capture and use is more efficient in fields that are well leveled and partitioned into plots," says Dr. Bhuiyan. ■

Escaping the floods brings a better life

Carolyn Dedolph

TANGAIL, BANGLADESH

In a land with no stones, where there's either too much water or not enough, and where nearly 900 persons inhabit every square kilometer of land, living is difficult—and farming is tough.

Mohamed Abdul Makim Talukdar and his wife Joygun Nessa live in rural Tangail, Bangladesh. The area is in the heart of the traditional deepwater rice area, where the clays are a tawny-orange color. The houses are perched on earthen platforms to keep them above the floodwaters that come with the monsoon every year.

Farming, however difficult or challenging, is the only life most Bangladeshis know. "I have been a rice farmer for 35 years," says Mr. Talukdar. "I started when I was 10."

But farming has been undergoing many changes during his life. One of the most dramatic has been a shift in the kind of rice that farmers grow, and the changes this has caused in the cropping patterns. Traditionally, farmers broadcast floating rice about 2-3 months before the onset of the monsoon in April to early May, and harvest it in November or December, after the floods have receded.

These floating rice plants are uniquely adapted to this flood-prone ecosystem: they can elongate their stems rapidly in response to rising floodwater, growing as much as 20 centi-

O. Rifanah & J. Requenco

meters a day in waters more than a meter deep. Amazing growers they may be, but these rices yield only 0.5-2.5 tons per hectare in average years. And in some years there is no harvest at all because of severe flooding or drought—or both.

In recent years, many farmers have substituted a dry season crop of irrigated rice, commonly called "boro rice," for one wet season crop of floating rice, more than doubling the yield. Groundwater irrigation projects using tube wells and suitable varieties with tolerance for cold temperature have been mainly responsible for this shift. The water for irrigation comes from shallow groundwater aquifers that are replenished yearly.

The adoption of dry season irrigated rice has improved both the availability of food and

All members of the family—sometimes even young children—are expected to work on the farms in Bangladesh.

R. Calbreth

farmers' incomes. Farmers can now consistently get about 5.5 tons per hectare using the modern varieties. Although the production cost of irrigated rice is almost three times more than that of floating rice, a farmer's net income ends up being twice as high, and the actual expense

per ton of grain produced is almost 40 percent lower with irrigated rice.

Innovative farmers, in collaboration with scientists from national agricultural research systems and IRRI, have been developing intensive cropping systems with nonrice crops

before or after rice. New seeding and crop production methods to fit in with the flood pattern are also being developed.

Some farmers, such as Mr. Talukdar, are combining irrigated rice in the dry season with deepwater rice in the wet season—instead of leaving the

R. Caputo

“I’ll continue to farm the land, but I would really like to go abroad to work, perhaps to Saudi Arabia as a laborer to make more money,” Mr. Talukdar says.

fields fallow during the rains. He grows an irrigated crop of BR14 and IR8, called “IRRI8” in Bangladesh, during the dry season (mid-November to late April/May). After the irrigated crop is harvested, he grows deepwater rice during the wet season.

He also tries new technologies on his nonirrigated land. This year, he is planting a mixture of Datury, a local early wet season or summer (April-August) rice variety, and Alloy, a deepwater rice. “We are now just waiting for the rains,” explains the farmer.

For the transplanted wet season crop, he uses the modern variety BR11 and a local variety Nigershail. Half of his land, which is rainfed and low-lying, is planted from April to November to a deepwater crop of Chamara.

The family also raises rainfed jute, wheat, potato, pulses, lentils, and sugarcane. Some of the produce is sold, but most is

consumed by the family. Vegetables, including bottle gourd, pumpkin, and beans, are also grown.

“We sell mustard and about half of the rough rice,” says Mr. Talukdar. He explains that the going rate for rough rice is 300 taka (US\$7.25) for 40 kilograms. For each *bigha* (0.13 hectare) of land, he grosses 3,600 taka (US\$87). His expenses—irrigation, fertilizer, labor, and one pesticide application for stem borer—total about 2,000 taka per bigha (US\$362 per hectare), leaving him with 1,600 taka per bigha or US\$174 on his 0.6-hectare farm. “I make a profit,” says Mr. Talukdar, smiling.

To get modern varieties to produce up to their yield potential, Mr. Talukdar usually applies some chemical fertilizer. Getting fertilizer when he needs it is the major constraint he faces.

In addition to the cropping enterprises, the family also owns eight head of cattle and raises some goats, sheep, chickens, ducks, and pigeons. Ms. Nessa is in charge of the animals. Fodder must be brought to them, for no land is available for grazing. Weeds—roots and all—are sometimes dug up and washed for fodder.

Muri makes money

Joygun Nessa’s life revolves around rice: she eats it; her family raises it on the farm; and it supplies her with a livelihood: making *muri* (puffed rice).

Rice and salt and sand—as a medium for puffing the rice—are all she needs. Ms. Nessa, however, does not use just any old rice. She recommends IR8 or BR11 for the best results.

To prepare her specialty, she uses a clay stove in which the fire is underground. It uses one-third less fuel than other stoves, which is important in a land

R. Caputo

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suffering from an acute fuel shortage. She has been using the stove for about 7 years.

Squatting by the stove, she stokes the fire by throwing fistfuls of wheat straw down the stove's holes. Sometimes she uses balls of cow dung, rice hull, and sticks for fuel. The heat produced is intense.

Over one of the holes, she heats up a large clay pot with sand in it. Rice in salted water is warmed in a small pot over a different hole. She stirs the rice with a *naruni*, a utensil made of palm-midribs bunched together.

When the right temperature is reached, she skillfully pours the rice into the big pot with the sand and swirls it furiously for 30 seconds. Suddenly, the rice becomes alive in a burst of steam and fills the pot.

Ms. Nessa knows exactly when the rice is done puffing. If she hesitates a moment too long, the rice will burn. With the precision of a master chef, she dumps the contents into a clay strainer and shakes out the sand.

The muri is warm and mildly salty, with a nutty taste. She makes it every day so that it's fresh for her customers and family.

She markets the muri in bulk and in small plastic bags at the family's grocery store. From 40 kilograms of rough rice, she gets about 26 kilograms of muri. For every kilogram of muri sold, she earns 20 taka (US\$0.48). Ms. Nessa usually sells 52 kilograms of the snack food each week, earning about 1,400 taka (US\$34). Her yearly income from this business is 72,800 taka (US\$1,760) in a country where women factory workers often earn less than 1,000 taka (US\$24) per month, working six, sometimes seven days a week.

If she would simply sell the rough rice in the market, she would get only 12 taka (US\$0.29) per kilogram. For the 80 kilograms of rough rice used to make the muri, she would only earn 960 taka (US\$23.20)—440 taka (US\$10.60) less.

"Muri is profitable!" she says with a smile.

When producing well, the two cows give about 4 kilograms of milk each day, most of which is sold. Ms. Nessa is also a successful entrepreneur with her own puffed rice business. She sells the snack food in the family's grocery store. (See sidebar.)

Ms. Nessa stores her own rice and wheat seeds in bins in their 10-year-old house, its walls made of woven bamboo mats. The seed potatoes are stored in a wooden box kept under the bed.

So how does Mr. Talukdar get the idea to do all of these things? Sometimes he goes to the agricultural officer if he needs advice, but most of the time "I'm doing these things myself," he says. When Mr. Talukdar was involved a few years ago in on-farm research on wheat, rice, and mustard with the Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute, researchers would regularly visit him.

Mr. Talukdar takes the lead in working his ricefields, although he does hire laborers. The couple's 15-year-old daughter and 12-year-old son don't have much time to work on the farm because they are both busy at school. Their parents believe education is very important. The son also runs the small grocery store in the nearby village. "I want him to run the business and farm in the future," Mr. Talukdar. "And I want my daughter to be a professional."

When asked about his future as a rice farmer, a grin slowly spreads across Mr. Talukdar's weathered face, and he laughs. "I'll continue to farm the land, but I would really like to go abroad to work, perhaps to Saudi Arabia as a laborer to make more money." ■

Economic boom is changing the face of rice farming in Thailand

Gene Hettel

CENTRAL THAILAND

Rice farmers Chumpee and Loogkid Sarakam have converted their 3 hectares from traditional deepwater rice to an irrigated crop. Although they've been able to scrape out a living growing rice over the decades, prices have not enabled them to make much of a profit until just recently.

"It took last year's major flood to raise prices and we fear such prices will not last long at a time when the cost of inputs (fertilizer and herbicides) continues to rise," Mr. Sarakam says with concern. "We can honestly say we don't want Kamol and

A. Javellana

Nopravan (their son and daughter) to follow in our footsteps. We want a better life for them. They should do something with their education off the farm."

The Sarakams' sentiments represent the feelings of many farmers in Suphan Buri and other provinces in central Thailand. The goal of many young people is to leave the farm. On many farms today, only the old folks remain. This has implications for Thailand's future rice production and its position as the world's leading rice exporter. Instead of passing a farm onto their children, some Thai farmers facing retirement are more likely to encourage their children to leave, and then they sell the land to a developer.

Samvuey and Jumras Amphansri, both in their 50s, grow irrigated rice on 30 *rai* (4.8 hectares) in Pathum Thani Province. They see the high-tension power lines and the construction creeping closer on the southern horizon. "We would

Chumpee (right) and Loogkid Sarakam want their children Kamol and Nopravan to have a better life than they have had, which means they will soon be leaving the farm.

D. Rifa'at & J. Recuenco

consider selling our land to the developers because we will never get rich growing rice," Mr. Amphansri says. "Even though the rice price has increased recently, it has been offset by the input costs of fertilizer and pesticides."

The Amphansris do not see much of a future for young people in agriculture—rice farming particularly. Five of their seven children have already found good-paying jobs off the farm. "We don't know how much longer our two sons, Aroon and Thonglaor, who remain on the farm, will stay with us to help," says Mr. Amphansri. "We know they will soon find better livelihoods working in a factory."

Thailand's economic success has spread from Bangkok and other cities into the countryside. The roads leading north out of the capital were, not that long

ago, flanked by small ricefields tended by the entire family. Now huge areas have been converted to industrial parks for factories and commercial centers—ricefields are rarely seen. Where agriculture is still practiced, large tractors do the tilling and combines on caterpillar treads do the harvesting. Farm labor is very scarce as laborers and young people, such as those in the Amphansri and Sarakam families, have already found or will soon be seeking jobs in the city and in industry.

In Ayutthaya Province, Somchit Pudchon, a deepwater rice farmer, surveys the activities around his 0.8-hectare farm where a large two-story house is under construction. “All of the nearby development is causing a basic change in the area,” he says. Water stays in the fields longer so he and his neighbors must go to the nearby Huntra Rice Experiment Station to ask for varieties that mature later so that their crop will be able to wait out the longer standing deep water. The new topography has altered the whole system.

“The best option,” says Mr. Pudchon “is to sell the land for house construction.” Ten years ago, he sold more than half of

his land—some 20 rai (around 3 hectares)—for 80,000 baht (US\$3,200) per rai. But now he knows he was too hasty. “Today, I could sell that same land for 1 million baht (US\$40,000) per rai,” he says with regret. Closer to the main highway, some farmers are getting 3 million baht (US\$120,000) per rai. “At prices like that, not many farmers are going to hold on to the land to pass on to their children,” says Mr. Pudchon. “With all the development in this area, rice growing will disappear soon.”

The concern for the future of rice farming is certainly legitimate in provinces such as Ayutthaya and Pathum Thani, which are close to booming Bangkok. But in Prachin Buri Province, some 100 kilometers

Somchit Pudchon is financing the building of his new house not from deepwater rice profits, but from income generated by his son who is working in Thailand’s booming construction business.

northeast of the capital, there is also apprehension among the farmers.

In Kabinburi District, Ahd and Saboo Sriwong, both in their late 60s, have been growing floating and deepwater rice for nearly half a century—and recently some rainfed lowland rice—on their 32-hectare farm. Nineteen of the hectares are devoted to rice and 12 hectares to fruit trees. They have successfully raised six children, but the Sriwongs are concerned that none of them will follow in their footsteps.

“Farming has such a low income and there are no guarantees,” Mr. Sriwong says as he points to one of the pylons below his raised house showing the waterline left by 1995’s devastating floods. As a result of the prolonged flooding, they harvested only 9 tons of floating rice (on 13 hectares), 3 tons of deepwater rice (on 4.8 hectares),

Samvuey and Jumras Amphansri do not see much of a future for young people in rice farming.

Ahd Sriwong would like to see one or two of his children take over his farm, but he doesn't know if it will happen.

composite deepwater cross (a mixture of some 100 crosses in which there is some IRRI germplasm). "Although it has not yet been officially released, I have been growing it on demonstration yield plots on my farm and have been selling it as seed to about 100 farmers," he says. "In addition to better quality, it has increased our yields nearly 1 ton per hectare—from 1.8 to 2.7 tons." Prachin Buri researchers will be sending some seed of the composite cross to the Flood-prone Rice Ecosystem Program at IRRI for further testing.

"I don't sell the seed to make extra money," he emphasizes, "but to spread the new varieties as quickly as possible. I am happy to do this for my neighbors and perhaps provide an incentive for them to stay on their farms." ■

A. Javellana

and 1 ton of rainfed rice (on 0.8 hectare), compared with the 19, 12, and 3 tons, respectively, they would normally harvest.

"Jobs in factories and industry are more secure and regular," concludes Mr. Sriwong. "There is just too much fluctuation in farming."

In a neighboring district, Mr. Juan Kongklom, 42, has resisted the lure of the boom to the southwest and has decided to stay on his family's 104-rai (16-

hectare) deepwater rice farm. He has been managing the operation since his father died and is supporting his wife, Payao, his two sons, mother, and sister.

For the past 3 years, Mr. Kongklom has been assisting the Prachin Buri Research Center scientists in experiments with a

As the sun sets, Juan Kongklom, takes time out to contemplate the approaching planting season and the future with his 6-year-old son, Piyachet.

A. Javellana

RESEARCH HIGHLIGHTS

Preventing the dangers of acid sulfate soils

To reclaim acid sulfate soils, farmers commonly use rain and irrigation water to wash the acidity away. But the drainage water, which is contaminated with toxic aluminum (Al), is usually washed downstream—to become the next farmers' problem as it pollutes the surface water. If the concentration is high enough, plants and aquatic animals in the canal network die, and the water becomes unfit for drinking.

Scientists from the University of Can Tho, Vietnam; Wageningen University, Netherlands; and IRRI are working to solve this dilemma in Vietnam, where about 2.5 million hectares of land are affected. They have been investigating the effects of land management on the amount of Al accumulated in acid sulfate soils during the dry season.

The researchers found that the amount of water evaporating from the soil surface dictates the rate of Al accumulation, overwhelming the effects of chemical reactions within the topsoil.

Mulching with straw can reduce dramatically the amount of Al accumulated in the top 20 centimeters of soil, and early plowing in the dry season reduces the accumulation by about half.

"Less aluminum accumulation in the topsoil reduces hazards because less toxicity will be leached to the environment during the wet season," explains Dr. To Phuc Tuong, IRRI water management engineer.

Scientists from the University of Can Tho and IRRI are also working on how to lessen the negative effects of leaching from acidic soils. They found that the amount of acid leached by rain depends on the size

Crystal clear water in the canals of Vietnam signal a sterile environment caused by pollution from aluminum leaching.

of the cross-section and perimeter of the large water-conducting pores in the soil.

Farmers in the Mekong Delta of Vietnam typically construct raised beds for upland crops because of annual flooding. This practice, however, contributes to a lot of acid being leached into the environment and polluting it. Certain management practices contribute to leaching, while others lessen it.

"The pores of the soil in raised pineapple beds, for example, are compressed because the soil is not disturbed for two years. This lessens leaching. But in raised yam beds, the soil is tilled every year and the plants are uprooted. All of the disturbances in the soil prevent the pores from being compacted, and this means a lot of leaching can occur," explains Dr. Tuong.

The scientists' goal is to come up with effective ways to modify how farmers reclaim acid sulfate soils, including assessing the associated environmental hazards of the process.

New test for salinity tolerance

Scientists have been struggling for years with trying to accurately determine the level of salinity tolerance in rice during the reproductive stage. Field tests were not reliable and took 3-4 years to do, and laboratory and greenhouse techniques were horribly expensive.

Using common salt and plastic pots, scientists at IRRI have recently devised a salinity tolerance test that is "simple, fast, and inexpensive," according to Dr. D. Senadhira, the IRRI plant breeder whose research team developed the procedure. Done in the greenhouse, the test is based on the principle of osmotic adjustment between soil and a salinized water bath.

"Scientists in the national systems and elsewhere will now be able to effectively screen for salt tolerance in rice," says Dr. Senadhira.

Tests with well-known tolerant and sensitive varieties revealed the technique to be reliable and easy to use. IRRI scientists are employing the procedure to test advanced lines in breeding programs for salt-tolerant varieties. ■

STRENGTHENING INTERNATIONAL PARTNERSHIPS

R. Cabrera

Scientists listening to farmers—making things happen

Carolyn Dedolph

TANAMBAO, MID WEST REGION, MADAGASCAR

Meet Rado, the farmer-extensionist extraordinaire. Formally named Roger Andriamirado, this unassuming, 34-year-old is the president of a dynamic seven-member farmers' association that shares information and results from field experiments.

The association collaborates with researchers from the National Center for Research Applied to Rural Development (FOFIFA) and IRRI, who have been working with farmers in the Mid West Region of Madagascar in a participatory mode for the past several years.

"In these efforts, we have emphasized on-farm experiments with new IRRI varieties for the rainfed lowlands," says Dr. Martha Gaudreau, cropping systems agronomist and team leader of the Madagascar-IRRI Rice Research Project.

Mr. Rado's group is heavily involved in farmer-participatory research, and its members, in addition to learning, have also been teaching the researchers.

The members plan their activities in conjunction with the researchers. They constructively criticize one another's suggestions, providing valuable help to each other.

"Researchers respect me because I give my opinion openly," says Mr. Rado.

"A few years ago, I didn't know many things about farming. Now, I can do research myself and find out what works and what does not, and which technologies to use," he says.

Two years ago, researchers gave the farmers 500 to 1,000 grams of seeds of each of five new rice varieties. The farmers

were asked to try the varieties and then tell the researchers what they thought. They did. And after cleaning their harvest, they started multiplying the seeds. In 1995, the farmers had 4 tons of seed to sell.

This season, Mr. Rado planted nine new varieties from FOFIFA and IRRI. Among them are X2509, X236, 2787, 1579, 1580, and Tsemaka. The objective of the trial is for the farmers to determine which varieties perform the best under different soil conditions.

The main varieties being multiplied and shared are X265, X236, and X2509. Mr. Rado, however, doesn't simply sell seeds. He takes on a much more important role as a "farmer-extensionist." When someone is interested in buying seeds, he explains to them the kinds of soils for which the varieties are best suited.

To prove his point, he recites, "X265 is for soils that are drought-prone; X236 is for sandy soils; X2509 does well on very rich soil—and there's no lodging problem."

In 1995, he sold 1.5 tons of seeds from these three varieties for 1,500 Malagasy francs (US\$0.38) per kilogram. "I didn't get much benefit from doing this because of the high production costs," he says. But Mr. Rado's motives are more than economic. "I really want to share these seeds with others, so I sell them cheaply.

"On-farm research is like an invitation from the researchers to do more. But the work is not only for the researchers. It's also for me," Mr. Rado says. ■

C. Dedolph

"A few years ago, I didn't know many things about farming. Now, I can do research myself and find out what works and what does not, and which technologies to use," says Mr. Rado.

PROGRAM HIGHLIGHTS

Strengthening partnerships

Accelerating progress in selected national research systems through country- and ecosystem-specific support programs and networks requires a strong commitment from all concerned partners. Increasing the research capacity of IRRI's national system partners helps to foster closer working relationships that ultimately benefit rice farmers and consumers in those countries.

Through this program in 1995, IRRI worked with national systems in Bangladesh, Bhutan, Cambodia, Cuba, India, Indonesia, Iran, Lao PDR, Madagascar, Myanmar, Mozambique, Papua New Guinea, Philippines, Sri Lanka, and Thailand. Activities from selected countries are highlighted.

Ten Asian countries sign accord to strengthen partnerships

During a March 1996 meeting at IRRI, representatives from the national agricultural research systems (NARSs) of 10 rice-growing countries in Asia established a Council for Partnership on Rice Research in Asia (CORRA).

CORRA's aims are to guide, facilitate, support, and strengthen partnerships among NARSs in Asia, and between the NARSs and IRRI and other relevant institutions, in an effort to better satisfy rice research needs. CORRA, through the NARSs,

Cambodia's government agronomist **Suy Sakkunthea** (left), a partner of CIAP's social sciences team, and NGO extension worker **Thlang Chinda** (2nd from left) discuss cropping practices with model farmers **Suam Ya** and **Phan Suan**.

will also provide feedback to IRRI on agricultural research needs of the Asian region, develop concepts for an ecoregional approach for research on rice and rice-based farming systems, and facilitate linkages with advanced institutions conducting relevant rice research.

The founding members of the Council are Bangladesh, China, India, Indonesia, Malaysia, Myanmar, Philippines, Republic of Korea, Thailand, and Vietnam.

"As the agencies through which IRRI makes contact with farmers, the NARSs provide the conduit for the flow of feedback on farm-level production constraints and on opportunities for improving farmers' productivity," says Dr. Ken Fischer, IRRI deputy director general for research.

Cambodia produces first rice surplus in 25 years

Measuring the impact of research and research support is often difficult. So many factors combine to create successful harvests that it's often impossible to single out any particular element as the key one. However, in the case of rice production in Cambodia, the unique

circumstances make impact measurement much easier to obtain.

Throughout the 1970s and into the 1980s, agricultural production and research in Cambodia were in a precarious state. Seriously affected by the US-Vietnam war, by its own civil war, and gravely damaged in the years of Pol Pot's Khmer Rouge regime, the research and extension infrastructure had been totally destroyed by the time that relatively peaceful conditions were restored.

Much of the irrigated riceland was unusable, due to the destruction and lack of maintenance of the irrigation systems and to the large-scale laying of anti-personnel mines in and around the ricefields where battles were being fought. The agricultural research facilities no longer existed. Most of the researchers had disappeared—into the killing fields or out of the country. Many of Cambodia's traditional varieties were lost as the rice area contracted to 20 percent of its former level and seed stocks were consumed by hungry war refugees. The chances of the country producing enough rice to feed its people did not look good.

Then, in 1986, the Cambodian government invited IRRI to help it

M. Lempontik

Checking the quality of seed from new rice varieties, Kap Srau Rice Research Station, Cambodia.

restore its rice production capability to what it had been before the troubled 1970s, when the country was an exporter of the cereal. In 1987, with financial support from Australia, IRRI launched the Cambodia-IRRI-Australia Project (CIAP) to help the country's Department of Agronomy—and recently the Department of Agricultural Engineering also—establish and implement national research and development programs in rice production systems.

Since then, CIAP's international and Cambodian national researchers and support staff members have worked hand in hand with government departments, nongovernment organizations, and Cambodian

farmers to help the country improve its rice production figures year by year. Researchers and engineers have been trained, the infrastructure rebuilt, and Cambodia's national rice genetic resources restored from seed previously collected by IRRI and preserved in the International Rice Genebank.

The proof of the impact of CIAP became most clear in the first quarter of 1996 when a crop and food supply assessment, carried out by a joint mission of the World Food Programme (WFP) and the UN's Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), showed that not only had Cambodia achieved self-sufficiency in rice production for the first time in 25 years, it had produced a surplus for export.

Based on data from the government and from a community-level survey, the mission calculated that 3.3 million tons of wet and dry season rice were produced in 1995-96, 40 percent more than in 1994-95, and 30 percent higher than in the 5 preceding years. It then estimated that this would produce a rice surplus of 139,000 tons.

Factors affecting the increase in production have been given as the switch to higher yielding varieties, better pest management—both of which are technologies introduced by the CIAP team—and increased distribution and use of fertilizer.

The team leader of CIAP, Dr. Harry Nesbitt, gives full credit for the dramatic improvement of the country's rice production to the "excellent spirit of partnership that has existed between our team and our Cambodian counterparts." He adds: "Cambodians especially can be proud of this achievement. It is a landmark in the recovery of the country."

Specific accomplishments of CIAP during 1995-96 were significant:

- Cambodian farmers began once again to grow varieties that were "lost" during the country's civil strife. Samples of the seeds were, fortunately, preserved in IRRI's International Rice Genebank and later restored through CIAP. Six of these pureline rice selections were released in 1995, turning in impressive results during the wet season on more than 200 on-farm sites.
- About 450 samples of traditional varieties and 120 wild rice relatives were collected by CIAP staff in cooperation with the provincial agriculture authorities. About 550 traditional varieties collected in 1993 and 1994 were evaluated for

drought tolerance and photoperiod sensitivity. A germplasm catalog of this collection is being prepared.

- CIAP staff documented the pest management practices and perceived pest problems of more than 1,000 rainfed lowland rice farmers. To manage pests, farmers employ biological and cultural control, home-made botanical pesticides, and chemical pesticides. Of particular interest are reports of a plant used for crab control.

- The public awareness video *Grains of life* was translated into the Khmer language and released along with seven new IRRI training videos, bringing the total videos produced by CIAP to 16. All are in Khmer and are broadcast regularly on national television.

A Lao farmer sows seed of the shrubby legume *Leucaena* on contours, part of his on-farm research collaboration with the Lao-IRRI Project.

Lao PDR: building for the future

IRRI has been working with the Lao Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry since 1990. The Lao-IRRI Project is helping to develop a national rice research capability in the country, thereby improving productivity in the rainfed lowland, rainfed upland, and irrigated ecosystems. The Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation financially supports the Lao-IRRI Project.

Project highlights during 1995-96 include the following:

- Cooperation between the Department of Agriculture and Extension and Provincial Agriculture and Forestry Offices has resulted in the establishment of a national rice research network. By the end of 1995, the network incorporated all 16 provinces of the country and also Vientiane Municipality. More

than 100 scientists, technicians, trainers, and coordinators are active in the network.

- A cool storage facility for seeds and a glasshouse were completed at the National Agricultural Research Center near Vientiane. Also constructed were combined administrative-laboratory facilities at the Northern Upland Crops Research Center in Luang Prabang Province and office extensions at the southern regional rice research station in Campassak Province in southern Lao PDR. These facilities add to earlier infrastructure development aimed at providing facilities capable of supporting the country's national research and training needs.

- Lao PDR was granted associate membership in the Upland Rice Research Consortium and the Rice IPM Network.

R. Cabrera

R. Cabrera

Madagascar and IRRI sign agreement on research cooperation

The Ministry of Research Applied to Development (MRAD) of the Republic of Madagascar and IRRI signed an agreement to continue scientific and technical cooperation on high-priority research for improved rice production and productivity.

This work will focus on varietal adaptation, nutrient management, crop establishment and weed control, water management, integrated pest management, agricultural engineering technologies, and human resource development. Activities will be undertaken by MRAD—through the National Center for Applied Research on Rural Development (FOFIFA)—and IRRI.

The United States Agency for International Development has been funding the Madagascar-IRRI Rice Research and Training Project since 1984.

Important achievements in 1995 include the following:

- Five varieties resistant to rice yellow mottle virus (RYMV) were tested on 25 farms at two locations in the North West Region. While all were found to be resistant in the field, farmers preferred TOX3211-1-1-2-2-1, TOX3219-51-1-3-1-2B, and TOX3233-31-6-2-1-1A because of their good yields and short growth duration.

- Representatives of FOFIFA, the Plant Protection Service of the German Agency for Technical Cooperation (GTZ), and IRRI met in November 1995 to review research results and discuss plans for controlling RYMV. Breeding for resistance will be the priority. To speed up diffusion in the North West Region, GTZ agreed to immediately support the multiplication of three RYMV-resistant varieties.

- Farmers from the Marovoay Plain, Port Berge, and Mandritsara tested the animal-drawn single- and double-gang cono-puddlers as an alternative method for land preparation. Farmers who no longer have access to tractors prefer this technology over the traditional method of

A day's threshing is completed in Madagascar.

trampling land with a herd of oxen. One Marovoay farmer who has tested the cono-puddler for two seasons said that he has higher yields because the puddled layer of soil is deeper, his field is more level, and he has fewer Cyperaceae, making it easier to weed.

- A women's group in Bealanana tested the Indonesian model of a rice hull stove. The women found that the stove stays hotter longer, and it is more efficient than the ones developed locally.

- Mailaka (IR15579-24-2) is now widely grown throughout the Mid West Region after being introduced by the IRRI/FOFIFA regional research team during the 1992 main season. Several farmers have multiplied their first acquisitions of 500 grams into several tons and are selling seeds to their neighbors. Mailaka is now the variety to beat as farmers search for higher yields. ■

An IRRI scholar back home

DAUDKANDI, COMILLA, BANGLADESH

What happens to IRRI scholars when they leave the Institute? Most return home to help farmers.

Dr. Uttam Kumar Deb, an agricultural economist at the Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, is a good example.

Despite having earned his Ph D only slightly more than a year ago, he is already beginning to have an impact on the farmers of Bangladesh. He is working to improve the sustainability of saline lands.

"We are documenting farmers' cropping patterns and then determining what kind of research interventions are needed," Dr. Deb explains. He is collaborating on the project with Dr. Mahabub Hossain, head of the IRRI Social Sciences Division.

After earning his bachelor's degree, he joined the Bangladesh Rice Research Institute in 1989. A mere 2 years later, he left all that was familiar to him to pursue a master's degree at the University of the Philippines Los Baños (UPLB). Once at UPLB, he applied to be an IRRI scholar and earned a Ph D in agricultural economics 4 years later.

Dr. Deb thinks that he has been very fortunate to go to school and receive training outside Bangladesh. He was one of five selected—out of 80 candidates—to work for a Ph D through a British Government-funded program.

His roots, however, are still deep in the clay of Daudkandi. His family owns a simple, airy house. They rent out their land—less than 1 hectare—in exchange for half the harvest.

His mother, a widow, has emphasized the importance of education to her children: all six of them have advanced degrees or are currently studying toward one.

"I feel fortunate to have been at IRRI," says Dr. Deb. "It changed the way I look at things." Now he's using what he learned to help the people who matter the most.

R. Cabrera

Scientists advance through degree and postdegree training

Scientists from national agricultural research systems (NARSs) can take advantage of opportunities for professional advancement through master's and Ph D scholarships and postdegree fellowships. Degree studies are pursued at universities with which IRRI has formal collaborative agreements.

In 1995, 182 scientists from 28 countries in Asia, Africa, Europe, North America, and Oceania participated in degree and postdegree training at IRRI. Forty pursued master's degrees, 80 were Ph D candidates, and 62 underwent on-the-job training. At the end of the year, 113 had completed their respective programs, among them 22 master's and 34 Ph D scholars.

In-country training for regional and national needs

Training partnerships and linkages among rice research institutions and universities are promoted through in-country courses. Regional collaborative courses are for an international audience, while national courses are adapted for a national audience.

Almost 300 scientists from 16 countries updated their rice science skills during the year through collaborative in-country training: 43 participated in three regional courses, 178 in 14 national courses conducted in five countries, and the rest in courses conducted in relation to network or consortium activities, or in those conducted collaboratively with other international institutions.

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